

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN EARTHQUAKE PREPARATION OF POPULATION, NEW FORM OF EARTHQUAKE PREPARATION

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur ilmiy maqolada O‘zbekiston Respublikasi aholisining barcha qatlamlarini zilzilalarda to‘g‘ri harakat qilishga tayyorlash tizimini Mustaqil Davlatlar Hamdo‘stligiga a‘zo davlatlar va ilg‘or xorijiy davlatlarning shu sohasi bilan qisqacha taqqoslanishi va natijalarga ko‘ra aholining barcha qatlamlarini zilzila vaqtida to‘g‘ri harakat qilishga samarali tayyorlashning yangicha shakllari bo‘yicha takliflar kiritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: zilzila, aholining barcha qatlamlari, aholi toifasi, seysmologik xavflar, seysmik xavfsizlik, mustahkamlikni ta‘minlash, zamonaviy pedagogik va axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, FVV Fuqaro muhofazasi instituti, hududiy favqulodda vaziyatlar boshqarmalari Hayot faoliyati xavfsizligi o‘quv markazlari.

Аннотация: В данной научной статье кратко сравнивается система подготовки всех слоев населения Республики Узбекистан к правильным действиям при землетрясениях с системами подготовки государства-членов Содружества Независимых Государств, а также передовых зарубежных стран в этой области, и по результатам включены предложения по новым формам эффективной подготовки всех слоев населения к правильным действиям во время землетрясения.

Ключевые слова: землетрясение, все слои населения, категория населения, сейсмологические риски, сейсмическая безопасность, обеспечение устойчивости, современные педагогические и информационно-коммуникационные технологии, Институт гражданской защиты Министерства по чрезвычайным ситуациям, территориальные подразделения, учебные центры по безопасности жизнедеятельности.

Abstract: This scientific article briefly compares the system of training all segments of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan for correct actions during earthquakes with the training systems of member states of the Commonwealth of Independent States, as well as advanced foreign countries in this field, and based on the results, proposals are included for new forms of effective training for all layers of the population to take correct actions during an earthquake.

Key words: earthquake, all segments of the population, category of the population, seismological risks, seismic safety, ensuring sustainability, modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies, Institute of Civil

Protection of the Ministry of Emergency Situations, territorial divisions, training centers on life safety.

In recent years, specific and targeted measures and efforts aimed at protecting the population and territories of our republic from seismological hazards have been implemented. In particular, conditions have been created for conducting scientific research in the field of seismology and seismic resistant construction at the level of world requirements, the material of the network of stations monitoring the strained-deformed state of the earth's crust, assessing the seismic risk and recording earthquake detectors has been created. - the technical base has been strengthened.

In addition to the positive actions described above, due to the fact that our country is located in a seismically active area, we regularly carry out specific goal-oriented programs and scientific research in the field of seismology to prevent seismic risk, protect the population, regions, economic and social objects, and our material and cultural resources from seismic risk. the need to increase remains urgent.

According to the relevant decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the following are the main directions of ensuring seismic safety:

- improvement of the legal basis for ensuring the seismic safety of the population;
- taking measures to reduce the level of seismic risk;

- control of seismic stability of buildings and structures in use and to be put into use;

- control of seismic strength of water reservoirs and hydrotechnical structures located on the territory of the republic;

- wide implementation of modern information and communication technologies in the field of seismic safety;

- implementation of modern methods and technical means of ensuring seismic safety and durability;

- improvement of scientific bases and technologies of seismic safety and stability [1].

Creating new forms and methods of preparing all layers of the population to act correctly in the event of an earthquake is also an important task among the urgent tasks defined as the main directions of seismic safety. However, in this regard, the government of our country has adopted the relevant decision and other legal documents.

The population of our republic - the population employed in the production and service sectors, including state administration bodies, local executive authorities, leaders, employees, workers and servants of other organizations, and military personnel; pupils of pre-school educational institutions, students of general secondary schools and secondary special, vocational educational institutions and students of

higher educational institutions; people who are not employed in the production and service sectors, including persons with physical disabilities, and tourists visiting our country are divided into categories.

Preparing the population for earthquakes, in groups organized within categories, in meetings and training exercises held by the head of Civil Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan, at the Institute of Civil Protection of the Civil Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan, at the Center of Initial Training and Qualification of the Civil Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan, regional emergency situations Departments are trained in life safety training centers, service and workplaces, all educational institutions, and directly at their residences.

is carried out using innovative technologies, integrated and distance learning methods, modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies, as well as independent learning.

In order to prepare the population for earthquakes, strengthen their theoretical knowledge and practical skills, improve the cooperation of FVDT forces and tools, as well as to assess the level of preparedness, command-staff, special-tactical training exercises and complex training exercises, as well as general it is carried out by holding events in the form of "Young lifeguard" competitions in secondary, secondary-special and vocational educational institutions [2].

The system of preparing all layers of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan for proper action in emergency situations, including earthquakes, member countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States and foreign countries: the Russian Federation, Belarus, the Republics of Kazakhstan, the United States of America, A comparison with the same systems of Japan, China, India and Nepal showed that there are differences between the systems.

Russian Federation. It was found that there are the following differences in the system of training the population of Russia to act correctly in emergency situations and in the field of civil protection:

Training of heads of commissions of local subjects of the Russian Federation and heads of federal executive bodies, equal to the heads of territorial commissions for prevention and elimination of emergency situations of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent, at the Academy of Civil Protection of the Russian Federation FVV;

training of heads of municipal self-government bodies and organizations and authorized experts in the field should be carried out every five years and they should participate in annual thematic meetings and training exercises [3].

Republic of Belarus. It was found that there are the following differences in the system of training the population of Belarus to act correctly in emergency situations and in the field of civil protection:

Training of leading bodies and specialists in the Republic of Belarus in existing traditional trainings, as well as in extramural and distance trainings;

- conducting training with students of higher education educational institutions on issues of safety of life activities and optional trainings, consultations, trainings, field exercises as well as special courses based on choice;

- training of citizens using social services at home by employees of social services in their homes;

Conducting comprehensive training exercises with FVDT services and local state authorities once in seven years [4].

Republic of Kazakhstan. The procedure for training the population of the Republic of Kazakhstan to act in emergency situations and in the field of civil protection is approved not by the decision of the government of the Republic, but by the order of the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic registered in the Ministry of Justice of Kazakhstan. This order also approved the procedure for training the population, informing and promoting issues in the field [5].

United States of America. In the United States of America, the National Earthquake Technical Assistance Program (NETAP - National Earthquake Technical Assistance Program) has been implemented in order to prepare the population for proper action during earthquakes. This program is designed to help state and local governments gain the knowledge they need to plan and implement effective earthquake mitigation measures. The program offers instructor-led training courses. NETAP is a program administered by FEMA to rapidly implement training in organizations and communities.

NETAP provides training and related materials on topics related to earthquake risk reduction. The trainings, which last from a few hours to two days, are designed for a wide range of participants with different professional backgrounds. NETAP training takes place in one of two ways: in person or online.

In addition, ShakeOut global earthquake preparedness training courses have been implemented in the USA. ShakeOut is an annual global earthquake preparedness training course supported by FEMA, the United States Geological Society (USGS), the National Science Foundation and others. Businesses and other organizations can register and participate in training courses free of charge. ShakeOut provides an earthquake training guide for businesses with training for workers and employers.

Of course, in the USA, there are various programs in the direction of preparing the population to act properly in earthquakes, and in most cases, public education is carried out through the Internet and on the basis of payment [6].

Japan. There are many disaster prevention training centers in Japan where you can learn about natural disasters as well as experience simulated disasters. The Honjo Life Safety Training Center is owned by the Tokyo Metropolitan Police Department and offers a popular tour that families can participate in. The parent and child participate in firefighting by either moving through an earthquake shown on the screen or using a fire extinguisher to spray water on the source of a fire caused by an earthquake (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Actions of parents and children

The Shinagawa Disaster Prevention Experience Center offers disaster prevention training courses for parents and children. The training courses are structured in such a way that you can gain experience by having fun using familiar objects. You can play a game of "disaster prevention flashcards" to learn about disaster prevention.

At the Sona Area Tokyo training center, citizens can participate in practical training that provides survival skills for 72 hours after an earthquake. The 72-Hour Live Tokyo Earthquake Tour simulates a live earthquake in Tokyo and teaches residents how to react. Residents are tested on a tablet device to use the virtual experience of entering an evacuation center[7].

China. According to the Law of the People's Republic of China "On Action in Emergency Situations" adopted by the Decree of the President of the People's Republic of China No. 69 of August 30, 2007, the People's Governments of the People's Republic of China at the Provincial level and above are responsible for emergency management. shall create and improve training systems and timely train personnel of national governments and other relevant agencies responsible for emergency response. In addition, educational institutions of all levels and categories should include information about emergency situations in the curriculum, teach them, and form the skills of students to provide emergency aid to themselves and others. condition[8].

India. India is a country prone to a number of natural disasters such as earthquakes, floods, cyclones, avalanches, landslides, forest fires and hurricanes. Aga Khana Habitat (AKAH), formerly known as Focus Humanitarian Assistance, has been implementing projects in India since 2002. Disaster relief, relief and recovery activities are a priority of the Agency.

AKAH has acted in major natural disasters all over India. The agency implements various disaster risk reduction initiatives to strengthen the capacity of local communities to prepare for and respond to emergencies. The agency's

network of volunteers is a major force in earthquake preparedness and education. Training exercises on large-scale earthquake response are organized by AKAH volunteer teachers in collaboration with the National Disaster Management Authority of India, State Disaster Management Offices and district level partners[9].

Nepal . Nepal is located in an 800-kilometer "seismic hazard zone," but there are no seismology or earthquake preparedness or public education programs in the country. Shiba Subedi, a Nepalese doctoral student studying earthquake seismology at the University of Lausanne in Switzerland, is currently working to change this

Figure 2 A lecture on seismology at a school in Nepal

situation through the Seismology Schools program in Nepal. Its dual purpose is to educate the local community through the Nepal School Seismology Network program and to make earthquake data available in the public domain. To achieve these goals, they created and distributed earthquake education materials for use in schools and held workshops to help teachers integrate these materials into their curricula (Figure 2). They also installed 22 seismometers in schools in central and western Nepal and made the collected data freely available on the internet[10].

Taking into account the procedure for preparing the population for earthquakes in practice in our republic and the differences in the systems of the studied countries of the Russian Federation, Belarus, the Republic of Kazakhstan, the United States of America, Japan, China, India and Nepal, the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan in emergency situations In order to act and further improve the current procedure for training in the field of civil protection, the following is proposed:

Organization of training exercises on the topic "Actions of leaders and employees in the event of an earthquake" once a month in all enterprises, organizations, institutions, regardless of departmental affiliation and form of private ownership;

The Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the Ministries of Pre-School and School Education, once a year in educational institutions "Actions of professors, teachers, educators, staff and pupils

and students in the event of an earthquake" organization of training exercises on the subject;

Organization of competitions on "Actions of Civil Protection Structures in the Event of an Earthquake" once every five years among the civil protection structures of all enterprises, organizations, institutions, regardless of departmental affiliation and form of private ownership;

The Institute of Civil Protection of the Ministry of Emergencies of the Republic of Uzbekistan for teachers of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation and Preschool and School Education and other educational institutions "Teaching to act correctly during earthquakes" courses organize Inter-departmental consideration of regular trainings on the subject of "Proper behavior during earthquakes" by teachers who have completed courses in all educational institutions;

Based on Japan's experience, a 3D and higher scale "Proper action during earthquakes" (in the framework of private entrepreneurship) will be launched in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, in the regional centers and in the city of Tashkent, which will simulate the process of an earthquake and make citizens feel the effects of a real earthquake. consideration of the issue of building training centers at the level of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Taking into account the above proposals, making changes to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 754 of September 9, 2019 "On improving the procedure for preparing the population to act in emergency situations and in the field of civil protection".

Reference:

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020 yil 30 iyuldagi “O‘zbekiston respublikasi aholisi va hududining seysmik xavfsizligini ta’minlash tizimini tubdan takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi PQ-4794-sonli Qarori.
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2019 yil 9 sentabrdagi “Aholini favqulodda vaziyatlarda harakat qilishga va fuqaro muhofazasi sohasida tayyorlash tartibini takomillashtirish to‘g‘risida”gi 754-sonli qarori.
3. Постановление Правительства РФ от 18 сентября 2020 г. № 1485 “Об утверждении Положения о подготовке граждан Российской Федерации, иностранных граждан и лиц без гражданства в области защиты от чрезвычайных ситуаций природного и техногенного характера”.
4. Постановление Совета Министров Республики Беларусь от 23 мая 2013 года “Об утверждении положения о порядке обучения руководителей и работников республиканских органов государственного управления, иных государственных организаций, подчиненных Правительству Республики Беларусь, местных исполнительных и распорядительных органов, организаций

независимо от форм собственности и населения в области защиты населения и территорий от чрезвычайных ситуаций природного и техногенного характера и гражданской обороны, а также граждан, которыми комплектуются специальные формирования органов и подразделений по чрезвычайным ситуациям по мобилизации” №413.

5. Приказ Министра внутренних дел Республики Казахстан от 2 июля 2020 года “Об утверждении Правил информирования, пропаганды знаний, обучения населения и специалистов в сфере гражданской защиты” № 494.

6. <https://www.fema.gov/emergency-managers/=NETAP>.

7. https://web-japan.org/kidsweb/cool/20/202011_disaster-prevention-educatio.

8. <https://chinahelp.me/information/zakon-knr-o-reagirovanii-na-ch-situatsii>.

9. <https://the.akdn/ru/indiya/gotovnost-k-bedstviyam-i-reagirovanie-na-nih-indiya>.

10. <https://eos.org/articles/bringing-earthquake-education-to-schools-in-nepal>